

ANALYSIS ON PHYSIOLOGICAL DATA

Retained trial data for each physiological sensor

	retained	% from retained trials	% from all trials
All trials	840	100	93,33333333
Temperature	798	95	88,66666667
Heartrate	377	44,88095238	41,88888889
Eye tracking	840	100	93,33333333

Eye tracking and time estimation

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), EyeSpeed.mean, EyeSpeed.std, PupilDiameter.mean, PupilDiameter.std

Pearson deltaTimePerception~EyeSpeed.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.04295821	0.0922448	0.02475654	0.4736

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~EyeSpeed.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0464031	0.0888207	0.0213058	0.5375

Pearson deltaTimePerception~EyeSpeed.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0604931	0.0747851	0.0071786	0.8354

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~EyeSpeed.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0439321	0.0912765	0.0237805	0.4913

Pearson deltaTimePerception~PupilDiameter.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.06462265	0.0706617	0.003033423	0.93

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~PupilDiameter.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0087101	0.1261068	0.0589670	0.08764

Pearson deltaTimePerception~PupilDiameter.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0301041	0.1049908	0.0376151	0.2762

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~PupilDiameter.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0759891	0.0592864	-0.0083901	0.8082

Eye tracking and performance

Variables: performance, EyeSpeed.mean, EyeSpeed.std, PupilDiameter.mean, PupilDiameter.std

Pearson performance~EyeSpeed.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.10345924	0.0315704	-0.03610922	0.2956

Pearson performance~EyeSpeed.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0942791	0.0408286	-0.026848	0.4368

Pearson performance~PupilDiameter.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1453471	-0.0109711	-0.0785161	0.02278

Pearson performance~PupilDiameter.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0557221	0.0794630	0.0119245	0.7299

Eye tracking and fatigue

Variables: reportedFatigue, EyeSpeed.mean, EyeSpeed.std, PupilDiameter.mean, PupilDiameter.std

Spearman reportedFatigue~EyeSpeed.mean		
rho	p	
0.009623609	0.7806	

Spearman reportedFatigue~EyeSpeed.std		
rho	p	
0.1343202	9.427e-05	

Spearman reportedFatigue~PupilDiameter.mean		
rho	p	
-0.0573071	0.09695	

Spearman reportedFatigue~PupilDiameter.std		
rho	p	
0.0471564	0.1721	

Eye tracking and time judgment

Variables: reportedSpeedPerception, EyeSpeed.mean, EyeSpeed.std, PupilDiameter.mean, PupilDiameter.std

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~EyeSpeed.mean		
rho	p	
-0.04527395	0.1899	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~EyeSpeed.std		
rho	p	
0.0086852	0.8015	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~PupilDiameter.mean		
rho	p	
0.0476497	0.1677	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~PupilDiameter.std		
rho	p	
0.1477409	1.714e-05	

Temperature and time estimation

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), Temperature.mean, Temperature.std, Temperature.start-end

Pearson deltaTimePerception~Temperature.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.08254527	0.0562326	-0.01321999	0.7092

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~Temperature.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1458461	-0.0078687	-0.0772271	0.02915

Pearson deltaTimePerception~Temperature.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0513081	0.0874480	0.0181571	0.6085

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~Temperature.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0462281	0.0924987	0.0232469	0.512

Pearson deltaTimePerception~Temperature.start-end			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.03687513	0.1017800	0.03260934	0.3576

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~Temperature.start-end			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0884231	0.0503277	-0.0191401	0.5893

Temperature and performance

Variables: performance, Temperature.mean, Temperature.std, Temperature.start-end

Pearson performance~Temperature.mean			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.01955169	0.1188200	0.04987348	0.159

Pearson performance~Temperature.std			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0576811	0.0810148	0.0117231	0.7407

Pearson performance~Temperature.start-end			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0368751	0.1017800	0.0326093	0.3576

Temperature and fatigue

Variables: reportedFatigue, Temperature.mean, Temperature.std, Temperature.start-end

Spearman reportedFatigue~Temperature.mean		
rho	p	
0.08779257	0.0131	

Spearman reportedFatigue~Temperature.std		
rho	p	
-0.2246401	1.38e-10	

Spearman reportedFatigue~Temperature.start-end		
rho	p	
-0.0993151	0.004984	

Temperature and time judgment

Variables: reportedSpeedPerception, Temperature.mean, Temperature.std, Temperature.start-end

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~Temperature.mean		
rho	p	
-0.03560373	0.3151	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~Temperature.std		
rho	p	
-0.1499201	2.114e-05	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~Temperature.start-end		
rho	p	
-0.1143331	0.001215	

Heartrate

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), performance, reportedFatigue, reportedSpeedPerception, Heartrate

Pearson deltaTimePerception~Heartrate			
95% CI	cor		p
-0.26597542	0.0111077	-0.1299705	0.07088

Spearman reportedFatigue~Heartrate		
rho	p	
-0.07896641	0.2737	

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~Heartrate			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1787496	0.1025830	-0.038853	0.5907

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~Heartrate		
rho	p	
-0.1011787	0.1604	

Pearson performance~Heartrate			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.135367	0.1463736	0.0056145	0.9381